

STUDIES ON THE STRENGTHENING MECHANISMS OF DRMMCS

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ABSTRACT

It is found in this work that the strengthening of DRMMCs consists of two types of mechanisms: physical and mechanical mechanisms. Physical strengthening is predominantly induced by DCTE of constituents of DRMMCs. Mechanical strengthening is contributed by the effects of local stress coordination, local stress division and strain constraint in the matrix, as well as the effect of interphasal residual stresses. According to divided stress coordination equation, the critical aspect ratio criteria of crack initiation are proposed. Some mechanical properties of DRMMCs can be predicted quantitatively.

INTRODUCTION

Although there have been many studies on the fabrication, treatment, deformation, machining, fracture, fatigue and strengthening of DRMMCs, there are many problems remained to be studied. Until now there are not quite convincing strengthening mechanisms proposed for them. Arsenault et al considered that microstructural strengthening in the matrix of SiC_p reinforced aluminum alloy composites is important for strengthening of DRMMCs^[1,2]. Takamura and Suresh found that the dislocation density in the aluminum alloy matrix are much higher than that in control alloy^[3]. These results verify a fact that strengthening of matrix alloy is essential to whole composites, and primarily expressed by the higher density of dislocation in the matrix. This increase in dislocation density is related with the difference in coefficients of thermal expansion (DCTE) of the constituents of DRMMCs^[4]. Moreover, fracture events of reinforcements (short fibers or longer particles) and interface debonding are

frequently observed^[5], that means that reinforcements bear quite high external stress locally. In this work strengthening mechanisms of DRMMCs are preliminarily discussed quantitatively.

STUDY ON PHYSICAL STRENGTHENING MECHANISMS

MATERIALS AND EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURES

Reinforcements dealt with are silican carbide particulate (α -SiC_p, normal size 2.5 ~ 45 μ m), alumina particulate (α -Al₂O_{3p}, 5 ~ 74 μ m) and chopped carbon fiber, etc. The materials tested are fabricated by powder metallurgical method, in which the raw materials are pure metal and ceramic powders (commercial abrasive products). The powders are mechanically mixed or wet mixed in organic solute, dried and then cold compacted, hot pressed or plus hot extruded. The samples are machined, heat-treated (520 ~ 540°C quenched, 120 ~ 160 aged to peak hardness^[4]), following mechanically ground. Observations of microstructures are conducted on transmission electron microscopes (TEM) modeled H800 and JEM-200CX, the samples are prepared by mechanically ground and ion-thinned on GL6900 THINNER. Microhardness tests on Versamet-2 optical universal microscope.

ANALYSES OF MICROSTRUCTURES OF MATRIX

The strengthening of the matrix in DRMMCs is reflected by such facts: (1) The dislocation density is much higher in the matrix near the ceramic particles than other zones (see Table 1); (2) The dispersivity of the ageing precipitates is much higher near reinforcements (see Table 2); (3) The grain size is finer near the particles than other zones. The measurement of microhardness manifests the gradient distribution of the physical strengthening level (Fig. 1 a, b). Moreover, the short-range residual stress induced by DCTE in the constituents could have some positive or negative effect on the mechanical properties (see next section).

Table 1. Dislocation density in the matrix (3~6 visual aera, $\times 10^{14}$ 1/m²)

position	Materials system			
	SiCp/2024Al	CF/2024Al	Al2O3p/2024Al	Mof/2024Al
N-I	1.74~	2.0~	0.49~	0.31~
F-I	~0.68	~0.42		~0.12
C-A	~0.18			

Note: N-I; Near the Interface; F-I; Far from the Interface; C-A; Control Alloy

PHYSICAL STRENGTHENING MECHANISMS

These features of the microstructure and property (hardness) of DRMMCs sufficiently prove that the strengthening is greatly concerned with the changes in microstructures of the matrix, i. e., the strengthening of the matrix plays very important role in strengthening of DRMMCs. These microstructural features of the matrix, such as dense dislocations and precipitates, fine grain size, can all be explained by thermal plastic deformation near reinforcements induced by DCTE, and physical effect of the interface^[4]. These mechanisms are all contained by physical metallurgical field so that they are called "physical strengthening mechanisms", which is differed from the classical mechanical ones (ROM).

Fig. 1 Gradient distribution of microhardness in matrix in:
 a. SiC_p/2024Al b. Cf/2024Al

Table 2. Parameters of the dispersed phase in the matrix (3~6 visual area)

Parameters	position	Materials system		
		SiC _p /2024Al	Al ₂ O _{3t} /2024Al	2024Al
area density 1/μm ²	N-I	1100		60
	F-I	662	520	
length, nm	N-I	46.7 ± 29.84		36.37 ± 49.26
	F-I	42.8 ± 19.94	43.12 ± 14.83	
width, nm	N-I	10.09 ± 4.14		1.86 ± 3.33
	F-I	4.8 ± 1.12	4.45 ± 3.11	

STUDY ON MECHANICAL STRENGTHENING MECHANISMS

DIVIDED STRESS MECHANISM

According to fuzzy theory^[5], under any unidirectionally external stress σ^A , parallel to z axis, and at any transverse section (x - y plane), let $\tilde{\sigma}_1, \tilde{\sigma}_2, \tilde{\sigma}_3$ be the average axial effective stresses in the matrix, reinforcement and interfacial layer, respectively, called "divided stress", and A_1, A_2 and A_3 the area fraction of them in

x - y plane, then the static force equilibrium equation can be written as:

$$A_1\bar{\sigma}_1 + A_2\bar{\sigma}_2 + A_3\bar{\sigma}_3 = \sigma^A \quad (1)$$

LOCAL STRESS COORDINATION MECHANISM

According to Chai's analysis of "Iso-strength"^[6], the average axial effective stress must follow a "stress coordination equation":

$$\sigma_z = \omega_1\bar{\sigma}_1 + \omega_2\bar{\sigma}_2 + \omega_3\bar{\sigma}_3 \quad (2)$$

where, ω_1 , ω_2 , ω_3 are the functions of microstructural parameters:

$$\left. \begin{aligned} \omega_1 &= [1 + ((a+d)/l)^2]^{-3/2} - [1 + (R/l)^2]^{-3/2} \\ \omega_2 &= 1 - [1 + (a/l)^2]^{-3/2} \\ \omega_3 &= [1 + (a/l)^2]^{-3/2} - [1 + ((a+d)/l)^2]^{-3/2} \end{aligned} \right\} \quad (3)$$

and a is the equivalent radius of the reinforcements, d the width of interface, l the half length of the reinforcement, R the half central spacing of neighboring reinforcements on x - y plane. According to Eqs. 2 and 3, it is easy to find that the divided stresses in different positions in DRMMCs are controlled by the microstructural parameters. So we define Eq. 2 as "stress coordination equation".

EFFECT OF STRAIN CONSTRAINT IN MATRIX BY REINFORCEMENTS

Generally, the stiffer reinforcements constrain the deformation in the matrix strongly, under unidirectional external strain. Figs. 2 is an analytical model in which the shadow area represents the constrained domain, and its volume expresses the constraint strength. Referred to Fig. 2 b) one can recognize that the constrained strength is proportional to $l \cdot w^2$. Let k'_c be the "strain-constraint-coefficient", thinking of unified condition, it can be defined as:

$$k'_c = 2\eta^2/(1 + \eta^2) \cdot \lambda / (1 + \lambda) \quad (4)$$

where $\eta = a/R$ and λ is the effective aspect ratio, equal to l/a . Under the condition of small deformation it is supposed that there is an approximate relation under macro elastic stage:

$$\bar{\epsilon}_2/\bar{\epsilon}_1 = k'_c \quad (5)$$

where $\bar{\epsilon}_2$ and $\bar{\epsilon}_1$ are the axial effective strain in the reinforcements and matrix at x - y plane.

MECHANICAL STRENGTHENING MECHANISMS

When the composites undertake macroscopical linear-elastic strain, it is suggested that $\bar{\sigma}_1 \equiv E_1\bar{\epsilon}_1$, $\bar{\sigma}_2 \equiv E_2\bar{\epsilon}_2$, omitting the interface layer, from Eqs. 1 and 3, it obtains:

$$\sigma^A = \bar{\sigma}_1[1 + A_2(k'_c E_2/E_1 - 1)], \quad \bar{\epsilon}_1 \leq \epsilon_0 \quad (5)$$

where, E_1 and E_2 are the moduli of the matrix and reinforcements, respectively, ϵ_0 the yield strain of the matrix. If we evaluate the mechanical effect of the

reinforcements by the proportion of axial effective stress in the matrix and far-field stress, $\bar{\sigma}_1/\sigma^A$, the mechanical strengthening factor can be defined as:

$$\alpha^m = 1 - \bar{\sigma}_1/\sigma^A = \frac{A_2(k'_c E_2/E_1 - 1)}{1 + A_2(k'_c E_2/E_1 - 1)}, \quad k'_c \geq k'_{cc} \quad (6)$$

where $k'_{cc} = E_1/E_2$. Fig. 3 schematically shows the dependance of α^m on k'_c . Thus, the physical strengthening level can be evaluated with $1 - \alpha^m$. At whole plastic stage, the following approximate relation could exist from Eqs. 1, 4 and 5:

$$\bar{\sigma}_1 = \sigma^A / [(k'_c A_2 E_2)^n (\sigma^A)^{1-n} / A + n(1 - A_2)] \quad (7)$$

where A and n are the *In Situ* work-hardening constants of the matrix.

Fig. 2 Schematic of strain constraint in matrix
 a. Constrained domain about a spheroidal particle
 b. Constrained domain about a cylindrical reinforcement

Fig. 3 Dependance of α^m on k'_c

EFFECT OF INTERPHASAL RESIDUAL STRESS

Regarding unavoidable interphasal residual stresses in DRMMCs, if $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}$ represents the axial divided stress in the matrix, $\bar{\sigma}_{ij}^{Rt}$ the residual stress, the effect of the residual stresses can be expressed from superposition theorem (take $\langle \bar{\sigma}_{ij} \rangle_z = \bar{\sigma}_1$, $\langle \sigma_{ij}^{Rt} \rangle_z = \sigma_z^{Rt}$):

$$\sigma^A = (\bar{\sigma}_1 - \sigma_z^{Rt}) / (1 - \alpha^m) \quad (8)$$

Taking σ^A as the characteristic property parameter when $\bar{\sigma}_1$ arrives at the related property limit of the matrix, such as proportional limit, elastic limit, etc., we can obtain predictive expressions of some strength properties of DRMMCs. Until now, the mechanical strengthening factors, stress division, stress coordination, strain constraint in matrix and interphasal residual stress effect as well, are all included into the consideration of mechanical strengthening mechanisms, referred to Eqs. 6 to 8.

STUDY ON FRACTURE MECHANISMS

ISO-STRENGTH EQUATION AND CRITICAL ASPECT RATIO CRITERIA

According to Eq. 2, when axial effective stress in the matrix $\bar{\sigma}_1$ arrives at the *In Situ* fracture strength of the matrix σ_{k1} , the matrix will first crack here; so do the reinforcements and the interface. If the stresses in two of the three arrive

simultaneously at corresponding fracture limits, this situation is defined as "Iso-Strength State". Take $\tilde{\sigma}_2 = \sigma_{k2}$, $\sigma_z = \sigma_{k1}^I$, and presume $\tilde{\sigma}_{k1}^I \approx \sigma_{k1}$, $d = 0$, we have "Iso-Strength Equation":

$$\sigma_{k1}^I / \sigma_{k2} = \sigma_1^I / \sigma_{k2} \omega_1 + \omega_2 \tag{9}$$

where σ_1^I is the value of $\tilde{\sigma}_1$ at the fracture of reinforcements. Iso-Strength Equation means that the composites with this microstructure possesses optimal design. According to the equation, the curve about microstructural parameters for certain material system can be plotted, called "Iso-Strength Curve". The curve divided the microstructural parameter space into three parts: 1. Iso-strength zone; at the curve, $\lambda = \lambda_c$, $\eta = \eta_c$, the foot-note c means these are critical values, the reinforcements and the interface fail in the same time, the microstructure attains "Iso-Strength State", which will bring into greatest play in strength properties. 2. Reinforcements fracture zone; above the Iso-Strength Curve, $\lambda > \lambda_c$, $\eta > \eta_c$, the reinforcements will crack first, and the interface and matrix are both safer. 3. The interface or matrix fracture zone, $\lambda < \lambda_c$, $\eta < \eta_c$, the interface fails first (debonding), the reinforcements and matrix are safer. Evidently, the microstructures of the last two states all produce lower strengthening efficiency. Fig. 4 shows Iso-Strength Curves of $\text{SiC}_p/2024\text{Al}$ and $\text{SiC}_p/\text{commercial pure Al}$.

Fig. 4 Iso-strength curves of $\text{SiC}_p/2024\text{Al}$ and SiC_p/Al composites

OBSERVATIONS OF CRACK INITIATIONS

The materials tested are the same as those in section 1. The longitudinal sections of the fragments of tensile samples are analysed on HITACHIS- 2700 electron microscope. Fig. 5 is a micrograph of a longitudinal section of $\text{Al}_2\text{O}_{3p}/2024\text{Al}$ composite. It is apparent that the longer reinforcements break in two or more segments. The analysis of the fracture in microstructures can be referred elsewhere^[7].

PREDICTIVE EVALUATIONS OF MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF DRMMCS

Rules of mixtures are the most famous methods of the property evaluations of continuous fiber reinforced composites, but there are few quantitative evaluating method of properties of DRMMCs. On the basis of the above study results, an exploring study on properties evaluation of DRMMCs are conducted, and here, taking fracture strain as an example. From McClintock model about a single coin-

like microcrack growing transversely in triaxial stress field, presume the original crack radius equal to the radius of broken or debonded reinforcements, and the stress triaxiality in the matrix far from the crack be:

$$T_r = \sigma_{r\infty} / \sigma_{eq} = 1/3 + \alpha_h k_c^I \quad (10)$$

where α_h is the triaxiality coefficient related to deformation pattern in the composite. For rigid reinforcements and linear work-hardening matrix, α_h is defined as:

$$\alpha_h = (E_2/E_1)^{2n/(1+n)} \quad (11)$$

Then from ultimate analysis, the limitation of crack growth is contacting of neighboring cracks, which initiate simultaneously. Thus we obtain the fracture strain of DRMMCs:

$$\epsilon_{ck} = 2\epsilon_{mk} \ln(1/\eta) \int_{\lambda_l}^{\lambda_u} \frac{f(\lambda) d\lambda}{\sqrt{3} \sinh(\sqrt{3} T_r) - 1} \quad (12)$$

where ϵ_{mk} is the *In Situ* fracture strain of the matrix, the integral of $f(\lambda)$ means the effect of the distribution of the effective aspect ratio on ϵ_{ck} , λ_u and λ_l are upper and lower limits of the aspect ratio. Fig. 6 shows the good agreements of predictive results with experimental ones.

Fig. 5 Fractograph of longitudinal sections of fragments of tensile samples ($Al_2O_{3p}/2024Al$)

Fig. 6 Comparisons of predictive (solid line) and experimental (marks) fracture strains for DRMMCs

CONCLUSIONS

1. Strengthening mechanisms of DRMMCs consist of physical and mechanical mechanisms. The physical strengthening mechanisms are contributed by DCTE of composite constituents and interfacial physical effects, reflected by dense dislocations, precipitates and finer grain size. Mechanical mechanisms are composed by local stress division, stress coordination, strain constraint in the matrix and the effect of interphasal residual stresses.

2. Mechanical strengthening factor α^m generally describes the effects of dominant microstructural parameters and moduli of the constituents on DRMMCs, and the strain constraint factor k_c^I is a better new variable instead of volume fraction.

3. Iso-Strength Equation is very useful medium to judge the crack initiating sites and to evaluate the material design. The critical aspect ratio criteria produced by the equation can quantitatively indicate whether the interface or reinforcements are

safe and the critical aspect ratio is not constant but the function of the strengths and geometrical parameters of the constituents.

4. The equations of predictive evaluation for the properties of DRMMCs can be constructed according to these results of the strengthening and fracture mechanisms. The mechanical properties of DRMMCs can be quantitatively calculated and well evaluated with those predictive equations.

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REFERENCES

1. R. J. Arsenault, L. Wang, L. R. Fang, Strengthening of composites due to microstructural changes in the matrix, *Acta Metall. Mater.* , 39(1), 47-57 (1991)
2. M. Vogelsang, R. J. Arsenault, R. M. Fisher, An *In Situ* HVEM study of dislocation generation at Al/SiC interfaces in metal matrix composites, *Metall. Trans. A17*(3) , 379-389(1986)
3. T. Takamura and S. Suresh, Effects of thermal residual stresses and fiber packing on deformation of metal-matrix composites, *Acta Metall. Mater.* , 41(6), 1665-1681(1993)
4. Quan Gaofeng, Chai Donglang, Song Yujiu et al, An investigation on physical strengthening mechanisms in DRMMCs, *J. of Xi'an Jiaotong University* , 28(2), 49-54(1993)
5. Quan Gaofeng, Chai Donglang, Song Yujiu et al, Micromechanical analysis and experimental observation on crack initiation in DRMMCs, *Chin. J. of Mater. Res.* , 8(5), 460-466(1994)
6. Chai Donglang, Liu Jinghua, Iso-strength analysis of microstructures in duplex phase materials, *Progress in Materials Science* , 4(4), 328-331(1990)
7. Quan Gaofeng, Chai Donglang, Song Yujiu et al, The micromechanics criteria of fracture in DRMMCs, In: *Proc. IUMRS-ICAM93'* , Vol. 1, AP15-18, Tokyo Japan(1993)